

The Scan4Reco Virtual Museum

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1. Introduction

According to the formal definition of a Virtual Museum [1] the latter is usually, but not exclusively, perceived as a digital entity that draws on the characteristics of a museum, in order to complement, enhance, or augment the museum experience through personalization, interactivity and richness of content.

A wide variety of scopes, context of use and core technologies have been addressed by the Virtual Museums developed up to day. For instance, they may serve the preservation, dissemination, research, exhibition of digitalized cultural heritage in an engaging way for a wide range of visitors around the world, with the intention to increase the interest for physical real-world museums and/or cultural heritage itself. Moreover, VMs may use virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR) and web technologies to represent a simple or more complex dynamic 3D environment where an administrator have the opportunity to manage the virtual exhibition by manipulating objects [2,3,4].

The current contribution presents the [Virtual Museum](#) (VM) developed within the framework of the EC-funded project [Scan4Reco](#) (665091). The design of the VM was based on modern architectural trends and the principles for immersive and engaging experience, through the use of the state of the art technologies, serving thus, the scope of facilitating the access and communication of cultural heritage assets, in a way that would be difficult or impossible to be accomplished with real-world museums.

2. Motivation

Serving the general scope of the Scan4Reco project, which is no other than facilitating the public understanding on European cultural heritage, the main objective of the Scan4Reco VM is to enhance the accessibility of the project's digitized cultural objects (along with their corresponding metadata) to the scientific community, the field experts and the general public via the development of an 'always-on' VR platform, easily accessible by everyone from anywhere.

Moreover, the Scan4Reco VM innovates in another way and specifically in the way it improves the user's immersive experience through SoA technologies, but most importantly by following the modern architectural trends. In this respect, the main design & implementation strategy of the Scan4Reco VM was the adoption of the architectural principles of physical real-world museums, so as to deliver a 3D virtual space closely resembling real-ones and thus, providing a user-friendly experience in familiar environments that may also increase the effect on knowledge gain, entertainment and interest on cultural heritage.

Last but not least, the proposed VM aims to facilitate the work of a potential VM's operator in managing and enriching/updating the exhibited collections. To this direction, the Scan4Reco VM offers a user-friendly managing system that is realized via direct inter-connection of the VM's platform with a dedicated database.

3. Design & Implementation

To increase the accessibility level of cultural heritage, digitized surrogates of the studied cultural objects will be presented together with their conservation related multimedia documentation, helping thus, to the increasing of awareness regarding the role of preservation and conservation methods in modern representation and analysis of heritage objects. Therefore, providing public access to project information, non-experts will be able to virtually examine a work of art or archaeological artefact, without having to visit a museum and will be also given the simulation tools needed for the validation of restoration techniques that otherwise would not be allowed to be applied on the real object.

Scan4Reco Virtual museum comes from a blend of the principles learned from making museums in the physical world and the perspectives that are offered by the digital one. In order to accomplish a smooth transition from the physical to virtual environment, typical characteristics of a real museum are implemented to the virtual world (Figure 1a). Virtual museum consists of a foyer, rooms (Figure 1b) and the cultural objects exhibited in

each room, associated with various metadata and relevant information resulting from the whole Scan4Reco framework (Figure 1c).

Taking advantage of possibilities offered by a digital space a configurable navigation system and a 3D viewer has been implemented. Two kinds of transitions are provided, according to users' previous experience in 3D environment exploration. Trained users will have the possibility to move freely in the 3D space using keyboard and mouse, in order to come as close as they prefer to the exhibited objects. An alternative way, aims to support less experienced users (e.g. the elderly, etc.), that can transit smoothly within the 3D scene by clicking on predefined spots on the scene's floor. This kind of navigation allows the latter group to have access to the most interesting part of the scene, by skipping the time and the cognitive load needed to move and rotate around the environment searching for points of interest. In addition, a dedicated 3D viewer (Figure 1c) has been developed from scratch, that not only implements, but also extends the capabilities of standard 3D viewers (i.e. zooming, rotating & moving the depicted item) by providing: a) a region where the item's description is presented, b) interaction control points assigned at certain regions/spots of the object, whereby the user can have an overview of further and more detailed diagnostics measurements from scanning modules of the project and/or metadata.

Figure 1. a) Example of adoption of physical museum characteristics: Exhibition room in Guggenheim, New York (source: <https://www.guggenheim.org/about-the-collection>) above and a Scan4Reco room below, b) Rooms top view, c) 3D viewer.

4. Potential improvements

Scan4Reco VM has been developed in Unity 3D, where objects and scenes, were implemented after typology and other modelling adjustments to be integrated properly in the game engine. So far, the foyer and four other rooms have been set in the Virtual Museum, but it is crucial to mention that the Scan4Reco Virtual Museum supports infinite expansion via the dynamic and efficient reuse of its template rooms. Extending the virtual museum's possibilities, a more dynamic environment could be supported, by the connection of the museum with a database and the creation of a managing system, in order for an operator (e.g. curator, restorer, etc.) to insert the objects in the virtual museum according to current needs. Finally, the evaluation of visitors' experience would give us an insight regarding its future capabilities and possible adjustments, which may include entertainment and/or educational perspectives [5].

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References

- [1] Virtual Multimodal Museum (2017). [The ViMM Definition of a Virtual Museum](#)
- [2] White, M., Mourkoussis, N., Darcy, J., Petridis, P., Liarokapis, F., Lister, P., Walczak, K., Wojciechowski, R., Cellary, W., Chmielewski, J., Stawniak, M., Wiza, W., Patel, M., Stevenson, J., Manley, J., Giorgini, F., Sayd, P., Gaspard, F. (2004) ARCO-An Architecture for Digitization, Management and Presentation of Virtual Exhibitions. In: IEEE Proceedings of 22nd International Conference on Computer Graphics, Greece, Crete.
- [3] Kiourt, C., Koutsoudis, A. & Pavlidis, G. (2016) DynaMus: A fully dynamic 3D virtual museum framework. *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, 22, 984-991.
- [4] Aliaga, D., G., Bertino, E., & Valtolina, S. (2011) "DECHO—a framework for the digital exploration of cultural heritage objects," *Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH)* 3.3 (2011): 12.
- [5] Barbieri, L., Bruno, F. & Muzzupappa, M. (2017) Virtual museum system evaluation through user studies. *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, 26, 101-108.